

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15148289

Students' Rights and Effective Personnel Administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

Odu, Patience A.

**Department of Educational Management,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.**

ABSTRACT

This study investigated students' rights and effective personnel administration in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population of the study comprised 193,436 students enrolled in 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, consisting of 91,215 male and 102,221 female students (Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2023). The sample size of 440 students was drawn using multistage sampling technique, representing 0.23% of the total population. Two validated self-structured instruments were used collect data. The Cronbach Alpha reliability tests were used to determine the reliability coefficients of the instruments at 0.87 and 0.77 respectively. The data obtained were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and simple regression at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a very high and significant relationship between students' fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration. A low and significant relationship was found between the students fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State. This study recommended that the Ministry of Education should regularly organize seminar or forum where teachers can have opportunity to interact with constitutional lawyers about the importance of observing students' fundamental human rights of fair hearing in the organization of personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. School administrators should be mandated to integrate due process into all disciplinary practices in the schools.

Keywords: Students' Rights, Effective Personnel, Administration, Secondary Schools, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The management of educational institutions, particularly at the secondary school level, has undergone significant transformation in recent decades as the principles of democratic governance and human rights have gradually taken centre stage in shaping the conduct and administration of school activities. In this context, the importance of acknowledging and protecting students' rights within the school environment cannot be overstated. At the heart of every educational system lies a delicate balance between enforcing discipline and safeguarding the individual rights of learners, who are not only recipients of instruction but also bearers of fundamental liberties guaranteed under the law. When this balance is disrupted, the implications often extend beyond the confines of the classroom, and sometimes culminating in a serious legal confrontation and a loss of public trust in the educational institution. Education, as a formal socialising institution, is founded upon legal, moral, and ethical frameworks that define both its goals and operational boundaries.

Law, as a regulatory instrument plays a crucial role in defining the scope of acceptable behaviour and institutional responsibilities. Igwe and Obasi (2005) aptly defined law as a rule of existence or conduct that is established by an authority that is equally capable of enforcing its will, thereby providing a structure and direction in the governance of any organised system. Within the school context, laws, especially those embedded in the Nigeria Constitution or educational policy documents are expected to guide administrators, teachers, and students alike in their day-to-day conduct. These laws not only regulate the internal dynamics of school communities but also define the extent to which fundamental rights are recognised, protected, and enforced.

Yet, despite the centrality of legal principles in the conduct of educational governance, a significant proportion of school administrators and educators in Nigeria are found to be unfamiliar with these guiding laws. Nwagwu (as cited in Peretomode, 2004), lamented that many instructors have never read the Nigerian Constitution or even the laws, principles, and regulations governing the administration of the educational system. This lack of legal literacy among school personnel is negative situation that may potentially weaken the operational framework of secondary schools, thereby exposing it to avoidable litigation and administrative inefficiencies. Appiah (2018) reinforced this concern by highlighting that despite crucial roles played by education laws in ensuring effective operations of the school system, they are often relegated by administrators who in a bid to do they want, presume such legal responsibilities an exclusive concern of legal practitioners. This attitude not only reflects a profound lack of understanding that fundamentally undermines compliance with legal provisions, but also fosters a culture of ignorance in which violations of students' rights are trivialised or downplayed, often without due regard for their legal and ethical implications.

This disconnection between educational administration and legal awareness has, in recent times, fuelled a rise in litigations involving school authorities and parents if students who felt that their child's rights were violated. The pattern of lawsuits, ranging from allegations of unjust suspensions of child, unjustified expulsions claims to allegations of discrimination and denial of rights (Osuji & Egbo, 2021). This legal dispute underscores a systemic gap in the application of educational law in the secondary schools. The reality that school principals may be held vicariously liable for the wrongful actions of their subordinates only further justifies the need for administrative leaders to be legally informed and proactive in educating their staff and students on constitutional rights and institutional obligations. As Peretomode (2004) argued, educational law encompasses the legal parameters within which both public and private institutions operate, and therefore makes it imperative for stakeholders to be well-versed in the relevant provisions that safeguard the rights of learners.

Central to these legal frameworks are the provisions of Chapter IV, Sections 33–42 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. These sections, as summarised by Igwe and Obasi (2005), outline core human rights that are directly relevant to the educational setting. These include the right to dignity of the human person, personal liberty, fair hearing, private and family life, freedom of thought and expression, peaceful assembly, movement, and protection from discrimination. Each of these rights has practical implications on the importance of treated students fairly, and with utmost dignity, ensuring that students' rights to personal liberty are respected in schools. For instance, the right to fair hearing implies that disciplinary actions such as suspension or expulsion must be preceded by due process, including giving students a chance to respond to allegations. Otatu (2010) defined fair hearing as a situation where authority is exercised in alignment with the core tenets of justice that define due process. It involves granting individuals the opportunity to present their own evidence, question opposing evidence through cross-examination, and expect that any conclusions reached are based on credible and substantiated evidence. Every individual in a society whether a student or not is supposed to be listened to whenever there is need. This is the constitutional right of such an individual to be listened to. The right to fair hearing is applicable even when somebody has committed a criminal offence. It is embedded under section 36 (1) of the 1999 constitution that in both civil and criminal proceedings, a person is entitled to fair hearing within a reasonable time before a court of competent jurisdiction or other tribunal established

by law (Nigeria Constitution, 1999). This goes on to assert that the right to fair hearing of a person is guaranteed at all times. Nobody should be condemned without knowing the particular facts of the case.

Similarly, the right to freedom of association guarantees students the liberty to organise or participate in legitimate student groups or forums without fear of victimisation. It is a right to form, join, and actively participate in organisations, unions, clubs, or interest-based groups within and outside school settings for academic, social, political, cultural, or religious purposes. This right empowers students to engage collectively in dialogue, advocacy, and self-representation, particularly on matters affecting their education, welfare, and rights within the learning environment (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2022; Legal Information Institute, 2023).

Freedom of association serves as an essential mechanism through which students can participate meaningfully in shaping their educational experiences while in school. When school authorities attempt to suppress or interfere with the lawful activities of student organisations, such actions may be viewed as infringements on this fundamental right. Gede (2014) has it that infringement on personal liberty is possible, where the principal refused to sign or issue transfer certificates and school leaving certificates to parents or guardian after payment of all fees. She further stressed that the principal or teachers can infringe on the students right to liberty by refusing students from taking examination which they have duly paid or; refusing a student from attending classes, graduation, detention of students during or after school due to non-payment of school fees or as a disciplinary measure against misconduct.

The school as a microcosm of society, must reflect the democratic values and legal protections that govern the larger polity. Alike and Amaechina (2019) characterised the constitution as the fundamental law that sets out the organisational structure of a state and distributes powers among various political and administrative units. Applying this perspective to the school system, one can argue that secondary schools in Nigeria must operate in a manner that is consistent with constitutional prescriptions, and ensure that not only institutional order is upheld, but also justice and equity. Unfortunately, the persistent neglect of students' rights, through ignorance or administrative high-handedness is deeply troubling and indicative of a systemic flaw capable of precipitating serious rights violations, child abuses, and institutional disorder that may ultimately undermine the effective functioning of the school. This flaw can further manifests in other forms, such as indiscriminate punishment, suppression of student voices, denial of access to academic or welfare services, and even the failure to address grievances through proper channels.

Effective school administration, therefore, cannot be pursued in isolation from the legal frameworks that define the rights and responsibilities of all stakeholders. As Johnson (2013) asserted, school administration constitutes the principal governing mechanism responsible for making decisions that affect both staff and students. It entails not only the enforcement of rules but also the facilitation of a conducive environment for learning, growth, and inclusion. Osuji and Egbo (2021) advanced this understanding by situating educational administration within the context of theoretical and practical framework that lays emphasis on the systematic coordination of human and material resources to achieve educational goals. Within this framework, the administrator must ensure that institutional operations are in line with legal norms and ethical standards.

More specifically, school administration can be dissected into various functional areas, one of which is students' personnel administration. Chahal and Kumar (2022) identified personnel management, often referred to as human resource management, and as the life-wire of any organisation, of indicating its relevance in mobilisation of school community members toward the attainment of school objectives. The scholars further noted that students' personnel policies include critical components such as admission procedures, orientation, discipline, counselling, medical services, accommodation, and general welfare. These areas are closely linked to students' rights, and any form of mismanagement in terms of applying excessive authoritarianism approach or inappropriate procedural oversight, could result in rights infringements capable of attracting serious legal consequences.

Nwakpa (2015) went further to argue that students' personnel management is a core responsibility of school administrators, and have to be designed to optimise the students' experience within the sphere of curricular and co-curricular programmes. Ukaigwe and Igbozuruike (2018) posited that the student population should be at the heart of educational planning and administration. The scholars argued that schools exist primarily for the benefit of learners rather than teachers or administrators, an perspectives that highlights the necessity of aligning student management practices with the principles of equity, fairness, and legal compliance. If these principles are undermined under any guise, perhaps through negligence or ignorance, the educational process will become flawed and vulnerable to stricter external scrutiny and legal backlash.

This issue has become more pressing, especially in Nigeria context, given the increasing discontent by some parents over the observed disinterestedness and apparent nonchalant attitude with which some inadequately prepared school administrators engage with the regulatory frameworks and reported cases of students rights violations. Some of the principals conduct school affairs with whims and caprices, thereby being predisposed to handling disciplinary issues on the basis of personal discretion or inherited practices rather than codified rules (Ukaigwe & Igbozuruike, 2018). This trend breeds inconsistency and erodes institutional credibility. The implications have far reaching negative ramifications in public perception, particularly in disciplinary matters where students' rights are most likely to be challenged. As Chahal and Kumar (2022) noted, effective student discipline must be founded on practices that promote responsibility, constructive criticism, and opportunities for student success. These suggestions align closely with democratic ideals and legal mandates, which form the foundation of contemporary school disciplinary philosophies, thereby reinforcing the notion that discipline and rights are not mutually exclusive but can coexist within a balanced and legally compliant administrative framework.

Ukeje (as cited in Nwakpa, 2015), offered a more holistic perspective by identifying core elements of students' personnel management that support institutional cohesion and student development. These include fostering goodwill among students and departments, enhancing school morale, improving discipline, promoting student problem-solving, and preparing learners for responsible citizenship. Each of these elements is not only desirable from a pedagogical standpoint, but also essential for upholding students' rights in a meaningful way. For instance, developing a sense of individual responsibility among students requires that they first be treated as responsible individuals whose rights and voices matter. Similarly, training students in ethical cooperation and leadership cannot succeed in an environment where administrative decisions are arbitrary and unaccountable.

Given this interconnection between students' rights and administrative effectiveness, the need for legal literacy among school principals and teachers becomes all the more crucial. The tendency to leave legal matters in the hands of external practitioners, as Appiah (2018) highlighted, reflects a broader systemic weakness that has hindered the integration of legal consciousness into educational administration. This oversight not only affects how rights are interpreted and enforced but also influences the broader institutional culture within which students learn and grow. If school administrators are to foster environments where students feel secure, respected, and empowered, then the knowledge and application of educational law must become an integral part of leadership development and institutional planning.

Moreover, the increasing rate of litigation against school administrators in Nigeria reflects a growing awareness among citizens particularly parents, human rights activists, and advocacy groups about the legal rights of students. These litigations often arise from situations where school authorities, in their administrative practices, willingly or inadvertently infringe upon students' constitutional rights (Nwatu et al., 2020). This trend poses a significant threat to the morale and performance of school leaders who may feel constrained or discouraged by the fear of legal repercussions. Nonetheless, it also presents an opportunity for educational institutions to reform their administrative practices by embedding relevant legal accountability requirements and rights-based approaches into their operational ethos. Schools must therefore move beyond reactive measures and invest in proactive legal education for all stakeholders, including principals, teachers and support staff.

In light of the foregoing, this study examines the relationship between students' fundamental rights and effective school administration in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It focuses particularly on right to fair hearing, and personal liberty. These rights are not merely constitutional artefacts but practical standards that must be enforced in the conduct of daily school affairs.

Statement of the Problem

The right to education is enshrined as a fundamental human right. It is recognised by both international legal frameworks and the Nigerian Constitution. However, the practical realisation of this right in terms of their enforcement is often compromised within the school system, particularly where students' fundamental rights are ignored or violated by school authorities. Despite the presence of constitutional guarantees such as the right to fair hearing, right to liberty and freedom from discrimination among others, it is highly troubling to observe a persistent pattern of students' rights infringement in Nigeria's secondary schools, particularly in Rivers State. Several empirical reports and decided court cases have revealed an upsurge in litigation involving school administrators, and often initiated by aggrieved parents and civil society actors who are concerned about the unlawful treatment of students. This administrative gap has led to growing concerns about the preparedness of school principals to integrate legal awareness into personnel management practices. The recurring violation of students' rights has raised questions about the extent to which school administrators understand and apply legal standards in the discharge of their duties, including personnel administration. Hence, this study investigated whether the recognition of students' rights have correlation with effective personnel management in senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the relationship between students' fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in Secondary Schools in secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in secondary schools in secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between the fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population of the study comprised 193,436 students enrolled in 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, consisting of 91,215 male and 102,221 female students (Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2023). The sample consisted of 440 students, representing 0.23% of the total population. A multistage sampling technique was adopted, involving stratified, quota, and simple random sampling. Eleven Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected, each forming a stratum. Four schools were then selected from each LGA, and ten students were randomly chosen from each school in line with Yamane's (1967) sample determination formula. Two validated self-structured instruments were used: the Students' Rights Questionnaire (SRQ) and the Effective School Administration Questionnaire (ESAQ). Cronbach Alpha reliability tests were used to determine the reliability coefficients of the instruments, which were 0.87 for SRQ and 0.77 for ESAQ. Of the 440 copies of the instruments distributed, 409 were valid, and the data extracted from them were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and simple regression at a 0.05 significance level.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between students' fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple regression analysis on the relationship between fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Degree of Relationship
1	0.792 ^a	0.628	0.627	Very High

Dependent Variable: Effective personnel administration, Predictors: (Constant) Fair hearing

Decision rule: .01 - .24 = low relationship, .25 - .45 = moderate relationship, .50 - .74 high relationship, and 0.75 – 1.0 = Very High relationship

Table 1 shows that the Pearson Product Moment coefficient R was obtained at 0.792^a. This implies that there is a very high and positive relationship between students' fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools?*

Table 2: Simple regression analysis on the relationship between fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Degree of Relationship
1	0.195 ^a	0.038	0.035	Low

Dependent Variable: Effective personnel administration, Predictors: (Constant) Personal liberty

Decision rule: .01 - .24 = low relationship, .25 - .45 = moderate relationship, .50 - .74 high relationship, and 0.75 – 1.0 = Very High relationship

Table 2 shows that the Pearson Product Moment coefficient R was obtained at 0.195^a. This implies that there is a low and positive relationship between the fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State.

Test of Null Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 (Ho₁): There is no significant relationship between the fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in Rivers State?

Table 3: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on the significance of relationship between the fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t value	P-value	Sig. Level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.657	.093		7.098	.000		
Fair hearing	.790	.031	.792	25.319	.000	±1.96	Significant Ho ₁ rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Effective personnel administration

P < 0.05

Table 3 shows that t-test analysis associated with simple regression yielded a t-value of 25.319. Since the t-value of 25.319 is far higher than the significance level of ±1.96, and thus establishes that fair hearing has significant relationship with effective personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Therefore, the above stated null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2 (Ho₂): There is no significant relationship between the fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on the significance of relationship between the fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t value	P-value	Sig. Level	Decision
	B	Std. Error					
(Constant)	2.348	.162		14.506	.000		
Personal liberty	.214	.055	.195	3.876	.000	±1.96	Significant Ho ₂ rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Effective personnel administration

P < 0.05

Table 4 shows that t-test analysis associated with simple regression yielded a t-value of 3.876. Since the t-value of 3.876 is far higher than the alpha level of ±1.96, and thus establishes that personal liberty has significant relationship with effective personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Therefore, the above stated null hypothesis is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed a very high positive relationship between students' fundamental rights to fair hearing and effective personnel administration in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This strong relationship suggests that the application of fair hearing principles plays a vital role in enhancing school management, especially in resolving administrative and disciplinary matters. One possible explanation for this outcome is that when school managers uphold fair hearing procedures, they are better able to investigate issues thoroughly and adjudicate disputes impartially. This in turn contributes to a more transparent and legally compliant administrative process in the school system.

This finding is consistent with the observation of William (2014), who explained that fair hearing is not only a common law principle in Nigeria but also a statutory and constitutional requirement applicable in schools. Supporting this view, Otatu (2010) affirmed that fair hearing is a fundamental component of due process, insisting that no disciplinary decision should be taken against teachers or students without giving them an opportunity to be heard. Appiah (2018) similarly reported that a significant number of students under the age of 18 in Ghana enjoyed various protections relating to human rights observance, including the right to fair hearing. According to the scholar, school authorities were found to operate within legal boundaries, reinforcing the notion that fair hearing remains a cornerstone of due process in education. This demonstrates that the principles of fairness and equity are deeply rooted in both national and institutional legal frameworks. Indeed, the denial of fair hearing to any individual constitutes a violation of their fundamental rights.

The findings also align with the position of Igbozuruike et al. (2018), who argued that school children, like adults, are entitled to constitutional rights, while also enjoying additional rights conferred upon them due to their student status-rights that do not extend to non-students. These insights are further supported by Appiah (2018), who found that 77% of students acknowledged that they knew their rights to fair hearing and non-discrimination, while over 64% indicated that they knew about the knowledge of their rights to a decent standard of living, protection, and well-being. Corroborating this perspective, Zain-Al-Dien (2015) maintained that school children should be treated as legal subjects with the same constitutional protections afforded to adults. The scholar argued that students deserve equal access to fair hearing, especially when administrative actions may affect their educational status or welfare. In structured organisations such as schools, formal patterns of activities are expected to follow established legal and procedural norms. Fair hearing, therefore, remains one of the most critical safeguards in disciplinary matters involving school authorities and students. It must be consistently exercised to uphold

justice, enhance credibility, and foster a school environment governed by accountability and respect for the rule of law.

The findings of this study also revealed that there is a low positive relationship between the fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in Rivers State. Despite the low relationship, personal liberty had a significant relationship with effective personnel administration in senior secondary schools in the state. The reason for this finding may be related to the fact that personal liberty allows both students and staff to exercise their constitutional right to act freely, provided that such actions do not infringe upon the rights of others under the This finding is not consistent with Ibueavunam et al. (2023), who reported a high degree of compliance among the principals on the extent they implemented children's' right to personal Liberty in government high schools in Ebonyi state. However, the finding is consistent with Igwe (2004), who reported that in the process of executing their duties, principals and/or teachers, whether aware or unaware of the legal implications, may detain a student in a room as a disciplinary measure, thereby violating Section 35(1) of the 1999 Constitution, which guarantees the right to personal liberty. Gede (2014) also stated that infringement on personal liberty may occur when a principal refuses to sign or issue transfer certificates or school leaving certificates to parents or guardians after full payment of school fees. She further explained that school authorities may violate students' rights to liberty by preventing them from taking examinations for which they have paid for, denying them access to classes or graduation, or detaining students during or after school hours due to non-payment of fees or as punishment for misconduct. Such actions, if unchecked, not only undermine the dignity of the students but also erode the foundational principles of justice and fairness within the educational system.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, this study concludes that there is a very high and positive relationship between students' fundamental rights of fair hearing and effective personnel administration. A low and positive relationship was found between students' fundamental rights of personal liberty and effective personnel administration in secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The Ministry of Education should regularly organize seminar or forum where teachers can have opportunity to interact with constitutional lawyers about the importance of observing students' fundamental human rights of fair hearing in the organization of personnel administration in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
2. School administrators should be mandated to integrate due process into all disciplinary practices. This should include ensuring that students are given clear notice of allegations, an opportunity to present their side, and access to a fair and unbiased hearing.
3. The Rivers State Ministry of Education, in collaboration with school principals and PTAs, should review and adjust existing school regulations to ensure that students' rights to personal liberty are respected without compromising discipline.

REFERENCES

- Alike, G. U., & Amaechina, O. U. (2019). Violation of right to the dignity of human person in Anambra basic schools: Challenges to quality universal basic education. *UNIZIK Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 3(1), 243–255.
- Appiah, M. (2018). Children's awareness of their rights in Ghana: The case of junior high school students in Aburi and Pokrom (Master's thesis). *University of Ghana*.
- Arop, F., & Obun, F. (2018). Denial of students' right to fair hearing and their unrest in the administration of secondary schools in Calabar education zone, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Development*, 22(3), 1–8.

- Chahal, D., & Kumar, R. (2022). A study of awareness regarding child rights education among male and female pupil-teachers. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 2459–2463.
- Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. (1999). Retrieved from <https://www.nigeria-law.org/ConstitutionOfTheFederalRepublicOfNigeria.htm>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (1999). *1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria*. FRN Press.
- Gede, N. T. (2014). Administrators' awareness of education law in the administration of secondary schools in Bayelsa State (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). *University of Port Harcourt*.
- Ibara, E. C. (2021). Education law and administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *South-South Journal of Humanities and International Studies*, 5(4), 97–120.
- Ibueavunam, J. O., Ogbonnia, O. N., & Oben, E. S. (2023). The extent of human rights implementation in the management of secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 10(1), 51–61.
- Igbozuruike, I. U., Amadi, C. C., & Onu, A. I. (2018). Education law enforcement and students-personnel governance: The challenge of 21st century secondary schools in Rivers State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 10(1), 96–103.
- Igwe, L. E. B. (2004). The law and the school administration. In P. O. M. Nnabuo, N. G. Okorie, O. G. Agabi, & L. E. B. Igwe (Eds.), *Fundamentals of educational management*. Versatile.
- Igwe, L. E. B., & Obasi, F. N. (2005). *Legal doctrines, principles and decided cases: Implications for effective school administration*. Fredsbary.
- International Labour Organization. (2022). Freedom of association. <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/freedom-of-association-and-the-right-to-collective-bargaining/lang--en/index.htm>
- Johnson, S. (2013). Types of school administration. 2006–2013 *Education.com*. <http://www.education.com>
- Legal Information Institute. (2023). *NAACP v. Alabama*. Cornell Law School. <https://www.law.cornell.edu/supremecourt/text/357/449>
- Nwakpa, P. (2015). Student personnel management: A panacea for effective secondary school administration in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(5), 62–64.
- Nwatu, L. U., Ebue, M. O., Ajibo, H. T., & Odo, C. O. (2020). Knowledge and awareness of basic provisions of child right act among secondary school students in Enugu State, Nigeria: Implications for social work practice. *International Journal of Youth Empowerment and Entrepreneurship Development*, 2(1), 273–284.
- Osuji, C. U., & Egbo, R. (2021). School administrators' awareness and protection of child's rights act in public secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 9(2), 1–9.
- Otaru, R. (2010). Access to justice and right to fair hearing. A lecture delivered at the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies on 2nd December, 2010. <http://www.otaruotaris.com/papers/ACCESS%20TO%20JUSTICE%20AND%20RIGHT%20TO%20FAIR%20HEARING.pdf>
- Peretomode, V. F. (2004). *Education law principles, cases & materials on schools*. International Universities Press Ltd.
- Ukaigwe, P. C., & Igbozuruike, I. U. (2018). Education law and community participation in financial management of secondary schools in Rivers State. *Educational Research International*, 7(3), 43–52.
- Wiliam, V. E. (2014). Customary courts and doctrine of fair hearing in Nigerian legal jurisprudence (1). *Daily Independent*. Retrieved September 18, 2015, from <http://dailyindependentnig.com/2014/11/customary-courts-doctrine-fair-hearing-nigerian-legal-jurisprudence-1/>
- Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An introductory analysis* (2nd ed.). Harper and Row.
- Zain-Al-Dien, M. (2015). Human rights education in Egypt: Secondary school students' perceptions. *Journal of Educational Research and Review*, 3(7), 101–110.